

RESISTIRÉ

Reducing gendered inequalities
caused by COVID-19 policies

Creating Safe Digital Spaces

Recommendations to policymakers to mitigate the gendered impacts of COVID-19, based on RESISTIRÉ findings.

The ever-growing importance of the internet and its spread and reach into the physical and social world are developments that have created new risks and that expose people to the threat of digital attacks and abuse. A crisis situation such as the recent pandemic, where these issues have become even more challenging, can be used to test new collaborations and solutions to address these problems. Social media and big tech companies could be a real ally in raising awareness, educating, and preventing the incidence of digital violence. Highlighting corporate responsibility and pressuring tech companies to not only recognise but also address the weaponisation of their platforms and take concrete action to fight this is indispensable for pursuing an equitable and safe digital transformation.

> Recommendations

Counter digital violence through education

Addressing the existing **cultural ignorance of digital GBV** that has been caused – in no small part – by the patriarchal organisation of our societies requires the widespread and general recognition of this problem. **Education** on this issue is **crucial**, although it is often (if not always) missing from curricula and a gender perspective is not used. **It is, therefore, imperative that modules on digital GBV are implemented in education from a certain age onwards.** Because it is an issue that transcends national borders, a European-wide system for education on this topic is needed.

Address digital violence in policymaking

Policymakers should pay increased attention to the various forms and impacts of digital violence. First and foremost, a **common definition of digital violence should be adopted and utilised in a consistent way in policymaking**, so that no conceptual confusion is possible. **Institutional policies and mechanisms for the prevention of and protection against digital violence are essential, as are support structures for survivors.** In this regard, it is important to adopt an anticipatory approach, swiftly adapting regulations to rapidly changing issues and new technologies that quickly emerge. A more **adequate response from law enforcement** to cases of digital violence is necessary as well. New policies and institutional regulations could be informed by the perspectives of survivors – for example, by having them participate in a process of co-designing policy.

Adoption of the directive by the European Parliament and Council

The directive on combating violence against women and domestic violence that was proposed by the European Commission (8 March 2022) should be approved by the European Parliament and Council. Not only would this have positive effects towards countering GBV in general, but the **explicit references to digital forms of abuse/violence could signal the beginning of more targeted policies against online violence and harassment.**

Hold tech companies and social media platforms accountable

Social media and digital technology companies should be held to account by policymakers for the digital violence that is committed on their platforms and for the **weaponisation** of their tools. These corporations should **protect** the people who use their platforms/products and **monitor** for any incidents of violence based on a shared definition of digital violence.

This could take the form of, for instance, improved tools for reporting and/or blocking users, as well as the countering of hate speech by prohibiting certain terms from being used or by automatically blocking messages that are deemed hateful. Increasing users' control over their privacy settings and the high-end encryption of all sensitive data and messages are other ways of preventing violence.

At the same time, **social media can also be a place of empowerment against digital violence**; platforms could institute public campaigns for social awareness, promote anti-victim blaming/anti-shaming, empower (digital) bystanders to be active and vigilant against abuse, and include the perspectives of women, racial and ethnic minorities, LGBTQI+ people, etc., in their daily functioning. All of this would contribute to a generally increased understanding that **digital violence is violence and that it needs to be addressed** in all its forms. Social media companies should even be encouraged to work together, exchange helpful information/tactics to counter digital violence, and implement measures to prevent/address simultaneous abuse against the same person on multiple platforms.

Design trauma-informed digital technologies

Digital technology companies need to adopt a **trauma-informed approach**¹ to designing and developing (new) digital technologies. Concretely, this means that **survivors of (digital) violence** are involved in the production of these technologies so that they can **identify crucial flaws and factors that could jeopardise women's safety and/or give perpetrators more opportunities to engage in violent acts**. For example, tools that give away someone's location can very easily be abused and should have safeguards in place to prevent bad actors from doing so. Moreover, transparency about the further development of these technologies is crucial, so that every (proposed) change can be scrutinised by survivors and activists.

Include digital violence in employers' anti-harassment policies

Employers with anti-harassment policies in place might, in many cases, still have blind spots, especially when it comes to harassment and violence in the online world. **Employers should, therefore, broaden the scope of their anti-harassment policies and update their equality and diversity policies** to include the digital dimension as a potential space of violence at work.

¹ *Trauma-informed approach to design* allows to consider how traumatic experiences affect users and find inclusive solutions that will meet their needs (<https://uxmag.com/articles/trauma-informed-design-understanding-trauma-and-healing>)

> Problem Statement

The Council of Europe Convention on Preventing and Combating Violence Against Women and Domestic Violence – the ‘Istanbul Convention’ – is the benchmark for international standards in this field. Yet **no specific legal instrument currently exists at the EU level to address violence against women and domestic violence.** The topic is nevertheless covered by several directives and regulations – for example, in the areas of the rights of victims of crime, equality between women and men, and asylum policies.

On 8 March 2022, the European Commission adopted a proposal for a directive on combatting violence against women and domestic violence put forth by the European Parliament and the Council of Europe. The proposal aims to ensure a minimum level of protection across the EU against such violence, regardless of whether it takes place **online or offline.** It proposes to **criminalise the most common forms of gender-based cyber violence** at the EU level: non-consensual sharing of intimate images and content, and cyberstalking.

Nonetheless, **digital GBV is still largely absent from the public debate** around violence and merits a more prominent position. One reason for this is the lack of a shared definition of online/digital GBV: if the issue is not named and outlined in clear terms, the risk exists that it will be severely downplayed or remain invisible.

> Insights from RESISTIRÉ

As a consequence of the increased use of digital technologies and social media during the pandemic (especially during lockdowns), the **risk of experiencing digital/online violence increased** for virtually everyone with a presence on the internet.

Despite this, **digital violence is not addressed in any of the National Recovery and Resilience Plans (NRRPs)** that were compiled by EU Member States in the wake of the pandemic. Moreover, interviews with experts and the outcomes of a workshop on the topic of gender-based violence (GBV) have indicated that there is a **lack of mechanisms (on the national level) to prevent digital violence and support online safety**, especially with regard to the safety of GBV survivors. Similar kinds of mechanisms are missing at the EU level as well, and the Istanbul Convention – which is more than ten years old at this point – needs to be updated to address the rise in online violence over the past decade. All of this indicates that there is an **urgent need for policies to counter (gender-based) digital violence and harassment**, on both a national and an EU level. The adoption of the proposed EU directive on GBV by the European Parliament would allow for positive development in all Member States.

Furthermore, there is a **lack of accountability** that persists at the level of **tech companies and social media platforms**, with a lack of real consequences for facilitating widespread online abuse and harassment. This trend is even more pronounced when considering the digital violence that people with a significant public presence – women and people of colour in particular – have to contend with on digital platforms. Faced with a barrage of **sexist, misogynist, and racist abuse, the intentional leaking of personal data, and all kinds of other threats, (potential) public figures can quickly be intimidated into silence and/or face devastating consequences for their mental and physical health.**

Moreover, the design of new digital technologies by large companies in the sector often does not take into account the perspectives of women and survivors of GBV. This, in turn, leads to **new forms of GBV**, i.e. the **weaponisation of smart homes** (temperature, sound levels, etc.), or the **facilitation of existing forms**, i.e. **stalkers using Apple AirTags**.

Lastly, digital violence is still often overlooked in employers' anti-harassment policies, the result being that there is the **potential for (gendered) digital violence at work** to become more prevalent than ever before – especially in light of the **widespread adoption of telework arrangements**.

A woman working for an LGBTQI+ support organisation in Slovakia expressed concern that the pandemic has polarised society even more than before and that the internet has played a major role in this development. Especially with regard to LGBTQI+ people in her country, she feels that much more hate and aggression have surfaced in the two years since the beginning of the pandemic:

“It has never been easy for LGBT people in this country, but nowadays the hate is getting out of the internet and into real life. We already have reports on physical attacks in the streets. ... I need to use [Facebook] because of my work, but otherwise I would leave it. It has become a horrible place full of hoaxes and hate, most things are extremely negative, particularly for LGBT.”

> Better Stories

Within RESISTIRÉ, we identify 'Better Stories', a term borrowed from Dina Georgis to refer to promising practices that identify how a given societal situation can be ameliorated to improve existing practices.

- **Maru the Chatbot is an internet freedom and safety tool that was developed by Plan International and Feminist Internet and was co-designed with young activists from all over the world.** Users can chat with Maru to learn more about digital harassment, how to report it, how to protect yourself from it, and how to support other people experiencing it. They can also make use of several guides and references to useful information. The development of Maru was guided by feminist design principles: it considers the potential barriers people may face in trying to access Maru, it ensures inclusive and empathetic language, and it represents a global perspective. [Find out more here.](#)
- **The annual international campaign '16 Days of Activism against Gender-Based Violence', organised by the Center for Women's Global Leadership, devoted extensive attention to digital violence in its most recent edition (2021). As part of the campaign, the UN Population Fund (UNFPA) started the 'bodyright' initiative, highlighting that corporate logos and copyrighted IP are better protected in the digital realm than images of human bodies,** which are often shared on the internet without consent and used for malicious purposes. The initiative aims to hold policymakers, companies, and individuals accountable, while simultaneously sending the message that women, racial and ethnic minorities, LGBTQI+ people, and other marginalised groups are valued and will not be violated online. Moreover, the UNFPA also launched 'The Virtual is Real' website, featuring stories of survivors of digital violence from around the world, as well as the work done by UNFPA to address this. Find out more at: [Bodyright - The Virtual is Real](#)
- **Digital SafeTea is an online interactive fiction game from Pollicy, an East African feminist collective of technologists, data scientists, creatives, and academics.** The game presents the stories of three young African women who deal with various expressions of digital violence in their life. Through these scenarios, players learn more about digital safety issues and are presented with concrete ways to better protect themselves in the online world. [Find out more here.](#)
- **CYBERSAFE is an EU-funded project that developed a toolkit to address digital sexual violence and raise awareness around the topic.** The toolkit includes tools that can be used in workshops on digital gender-based violence and it aims to promote responsible behaviour online among young people. [Find out more here.](#)

> About RESISTIRÉ

This factsheet is based on data collected within RESISTIRÉ's second research cycle, which ran from December 2021 to 28 February 2022. In this research 31 national researchers worked with the consortium to map policies, societal responses, and qualitative and quantitative indicators relating to the pandemic in EU-27 countries along with Iceland, the UK, Serbia, and Turkey.⁴ This research activity was accompanied by workshops and interviews with gender equality experts whose input informed the main findings from expert consultations.⁵

RESISTIRÉ is an EU-funded Horizon 2020 project the aim of which is to 1) understand the impact of COVID-19 policy responses on behavioural, social and economic inequalities in the EU27, Serbia, Turkey, Iceland, and the UK on the basis of a conceptual gender+ framework, and 2) design, devise and pilot policy solutions and social innovations to be deployed by policymakers, stakeholders and actors in different policy domains.

Find out more about the project at <https://resistire-project.eu>.

@Resistire_EU

@RESISTIRÉ

@resistire.EU

Discover all project outputs at <https://resistire-project.eu>.

Contact us: resistire_eu@esf.org

> Authorship and Contributions

Authors: A. Kerremans (YW), N. Wuiame (YW), A. Denis (YW)

Coordination and revision: M. Linková (ISAS), A. Kolasinska (ISAS)

Infographics: G. Romeo (YW)

> Acknowledgement and Disclaimer

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101015990.

The contents of this publication are the sole responsibility of its authors and do not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union.